

Adoption of the Nordic Balance Model, as a Security Regime in Ukraine

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Abstract

For a suggested solution of the ongoing war in Eastern Europe to be viable, it must meet the security needs of Russia, Ukraine and the separatist regions of Luhansk and Donetsk simultaneously. To achieve this, we must alter our point of view and widen our perspective so that the entire European continent will be included.

Such a way of thinking which contributed to the security in Northern Europe throughout the Cold War, and which can be reproduced in Eastern Europe is the "Nordic Balance" model. In this framework, the USSR was on one side, the NATO-member Scandinavian countries were on the other and neutral Finland and Sweden were in the middle, serving as buffer states. **Thus, becoming regional powers,** who serve as a **stabilizing factor** in the sub – system.

In Eastern Europe, for reasons that will be clear in the course of this paper, Russia can assume the role of the USSR on one pole, the West European NATO member countries, can play the part of Denmark and Norway on the other, and Ukraine and the regions of Luhansk and Donetsk can serve as buffer states, taking the role of Sweden and Finland, thus becoming the hearth of the model.

The mutual dependence arising from such a situation, the fact that each country safeguards the neutrality of the other, **is what ensures stability.**

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A new perspective

During the Vietnam war, Secretary of Defense Robert S. McNamara was asked by his generals to authorize additional troops, based on their belief that two decades of experience in Vietnam would assure victory. McNamara countered that, far from accumulating twenty years of experience, the US had simply repeated one year's worth of mistakes for twenty years.

Similarly, those who look with equal parts of optimism and frustration at years of failed peace initiatives between Russia and Ukraine are ignoring the fact that each "new" plan has been nothing more than a repetition of past unsuccessful efforts.

The Russian invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 substantially undermined the security situation extant in Europe since the Second World War. With the ongoing potential for escalation between Russia and the West, developments force states to calculate new routes in a changing reality.

History teaches that small states cannot take their survival for granted. For example Athens decreed that Melos should be wiped out, despite the islands efforts to stay out of the Peloponnesian War. Other small states, in more recent history, such as Estonia, Czechoslovakia and Kuwait suffered at the hands of large, threatening neighbors, sometimes to the point of loss of territory or independence or even destruction (Feldman 2023).

The small state will try, in these circumstances, to encourage its rivals to adopt international norms, rules and laws, join institutions and embed democratic values and patterns and market economy in its rival's society and regime to advance mutual dependence. In other words, the small state will ascribe a central role to soft power in its security strategy and rely less on military strength, and will try in this manner to moderate the aggressiveness of its neighbor peacefully (Keohane & Nye, 1977; Miller,2010; Neumann & Gstohl, 2006; Nye,2002; Rosecrance, 1986; Russell,2020). Sometimes a small state will use soft power to position itself as a leading actor in

international organizations and institutions, form small state coalitions in order to leverage their collective influence and widen their room for maneuver (Chong,2010; Nye,2009; Pape, 2005; Rickli, 2008). Against the balance of threat theory, Kiev sought to reduce the danger it faced from its neighbor by bringing Moscow closer to Europe through soft power, at a time when the environment changed at the end of the Cold War and Moscow was relatively weak.

On the other hand, when a great power is equipping its military, especially when it uses belligerent means to harm the sovereignty of an ally or neighbor or takes unilateral steps that violate international norms and law, these measures signal its

aggressive intentions. In accordance with the perception of intentions component of the balance of threat theory, the small state will realize under these conditions that it has reduced room for maneuver. Its threat perception will thus become more severe. Alongside cultivating its military strength, it will pursue a policy of assertive diplomacy, which includes imposing legal, institutional and normative restrictions on the threatening power with the aim of reducing the latter's overall superiority, harming its international legitimacy, and restraining it (Feldman 2023).

For a suggested solution of the ongoing East European conflict and war to be viable, it must meet the security needs of Russia, the NATO member European States and those of Ukraine simultaneously. To achieve this, we must alter our point of view, widen our perspective so that the entire European continent will be included and to seek for a solution that will be based on balance of power.

The term **balance of power** refers to the general concept of one or more states' power being used to balance that of another state or group of states. According to this way of thinking, in the anarchy of the international system, the most reliable brake on the power of one state, is the power of other states. Balance of power can refer to any ratio of power capabilities between states or alliances, or it can mean only a relatively equal ratio. Alternatively, balance of power can refer to the process by which counterbalancing coalitions have repeatedly formed in history to prevent one state from conquering an entire region.(Goldstein & Prevehouse;2010).

The theory of balance of power argues that such counterbalancing occurs regularly and maintains the stability of the international system. The system is stable in that its rules and principles stay the same: state sovereignty does not collapse into a universal empire. It is important to emphasize however, that this stability does not imply peace. It is rather a stability maintained by means of recurring wars that adjust power relations.

Such a way of thinking which contributed to the security of Northern Europe throughout the Cold War and which can be reproduced in the eastern part of the continent now, is the "Nordic Balance" model. In this framework, the USSR was on one side, the NATO member Scandinavian countries were on the other and neutral Finland and Sweden were in the middle, serving as buffer states. Thus becoming regional powers, who serve as stabilizing factor in the sub- system.

Sweden and Finland together constituted a kind of international strategic vacuum in the grey zone between the blocks, and as in nature, so too in international politics, a vacuum is a condition which has a tendency to be filled. This state of affairs turned these two states into mutually dependent "Siamese twins", where any change in the geopolitical status of one, would immediately result in a change in the geopolitical situation of the other. Possible scenarios at the time, could have been, for example, a Soviet invasion of Finland resulting from Sweden's increasing ties with NATO, or

Sweden joining NATO in reaction of Finland coming closer to the Eastern block, or one of the two becoming an isolated buffer state, an impossible situation on the long run.

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in Eastern Europe today, as in Scandinavia during the post-war era, one can find a geostrategic reality which prefers a situation in which two neighboring political entities are bonded together as neutrals between two blocks.

Since it is not unrealistic to assume that the faith of the separatist regions of Eastern Ukraine – Luhansk and Donetsk – whether as an independent entity or in some autonomous custom will be discussed as part of a permanent settlement (**I.A. in order to prevent humiliating Russia**), we can find here too as in Scandinavia during the Cold War, a situation consisted of two political entities between two rival blocks.

In East Europe, Ukraine can fulfill the role of Sweden in the Scandinavian sub-system, and the separatist region – the role of Finland.

The significant political change that must take place in Eastern Europe, if the intention is to adopt the Nordic Balance model, will be characterized by the turning of Ukraine and the future separatist region into neutral entities.

Neutrality is perceived as an attractive policy for small nations, which, because of their strategic location or symbolic political values, stand or may stand in the focus of a struggle for influence or control by regional or global rivals. The neutral state is a country whose political independence and territorial integrity enjoy the permanent recognition of the superpowers, provided that the neutral country does not use weapons against another country except for self-defense and does not enter into contractual obligations with any party that might endanger its status.

The object of neutrality is to preserve international order, to reduce tensions in the system and to bring international disputes to a solution based on agreed norms and institutions. From the point of view of the neutral state, the objective of neutrality is to defend its military security as well as preserve its political and territorial integrity. From the standpoint of the nations bordering the neutral state, the object of neutrality is to preserve the balance of power from being violated.

A distinction which is particularly apposite in this case is the division of neutrality into positive and negative aspects. The positive aspect in the policy of neutrality denotes the complex attempts made by neutral states to make their neutrality as attractive as possible to the contesting sides. This aspect incorporates a series of political measures carried out simultaneously on two planes: one, measures intended

to reduce fears of the contending sides regarding possible damage that might be caused to them by the neutrality of the small country; two – steps intended to strengthen their interest to continue to preserve neutrality.

The negative aspect of neutralist policy refers to deterring the contending sides from violating neutrality by convincing them that the price they would have to pay for such a step will be high. Such deterrence is based on military power.

Since this division is hypothetical, it would be more correct to distinguish between "negative – positive" neutrality, which puts the emphasis first on military deterrence and only afterwards on political reliability, and "positive – negative" neutrality which first underlines reliability and only then deterrence. This is precisely the distinction between the neutrality of Sweden and Finland, respectively. The same distinction would apply to Ukraine and the separatist regions of Luhansk and Donetsk, also respectively.

Contrary to Scandinavia, where neutrality can be defined as traditional neutrality, an attribute of which is freedom of choice, the more appropriate term for the neutrality applicable to Eastern Europe would be neutralization, in the context of which neutrality would be imposed on the state by means of international agreements. The outstanding characteristic of such a nation is that it is not neutral out of choice and, accordingly, cannot change its status according to its own wishes. In Eastern Europe, so filled with suspicions, this would somehow contribute to stability.

It is important to mention that neutrality is not an ideological asset: both Finland and Sweden in Northern Europe, and Austria and Switzerland in Central Europe, even as neutral states, belonged ideologically clearly to the western block.

The main difference between the "Nordic Balance" model and the intention to neutralize Ukraine as part of a future settlement - as has been suggested-is that in Eastern Europe we are referring to a sole neutral state as a buffer between the west and Russia. As we can learn from history (that of Poland during the 20:th century for example), that is not a desirable situation in the long run, since all of the borders of the neutral buffer state, are thus confrontational.

Dyads of neutrals between rival blocks, gives each of them the status of rim – states, instead of buffer – states.

As mentioned before, even since the fate of the separatist regions of Eastern Ukraine is not clear yet, it should be noted that the question of the preferences regarding the future of these areas as a sovereign state or as something less, within the context of a federation or confederation with Ukraine are irrelevant. An examination of recent processes in the international context, especially in Europe in the post cold war era, show that the question of "nationalism" or "supra-

nationalism" is a function of political development; in the modern era, the future seems to lie in the systems of blocks, provided that these are freely chosen (otherwise we're talking about colonialism). In order to achieve political unity of either kind, as in Western Europe for example or as East and West Ukraine confederation proposals advocate, a relatively homogenous group of sovereign states with many years of sovereignty is required. Assets, including sovereignty, cannot be relinquished unless they exist. The cases of former Soviet Union and Yugoslavia show what can be expected when an attempt is made to shorten these developmental processes by skipping over the initial stage of sovereignty. Introducing such a Trojan horse into our backyard would be unwise.

In connection with the different shades of neutrality, as also mentioned before, here too the Nordic case can serve as a model for what can be implemented in Eastern Europe. In addition, the Soviet – Finnish border corrections as well as restrictions regarding the size and quality of the Finnish army determined in bilateral Soviet – Finnish agreements can serve as precedents.

Advantages

This proposal, seems to be advantageous to all parties involved: Russia will safeguard her security interests in the west and achieve regional and international recognition regarding these interests. Luhansk and Donetsk will gain independence anchored in international agreements. Ukraine will achieve international standing and a national role similar to that of Sweden during the cold war. She will become a rim state instead of a buffer state, while protecting her global and regional interests. The entire region will gain stability, even without a clear solution to the East – West tension. This will be achieved thanks to the existence of a subsystem composed of nations, which balance one another, with a dyad of two neutral countries in between, serving together as a regional buffer power.

"Peace by balance" to quote Raymond Aaron.

One of the known obstacles that prevent a successful move from a state of hostility to a state of peace lay in the necessity to change negative attitudes, beliefs and values concerning the opposite side. Paradoxically, the best way to achieve this goal, is by living in peace with each other but one will not do that, prior to these attitude changes. By adopting the framework recommended here, the parties can sign a formal agreement, based on stability, and later, turn to attitude changes by establishing sorts of "Truth and reconciliation committees".

In a speech President Kennedy delivered in the summer of 1963, he mentioned I.A., as a lesson from the Cuban Missile Crisis, less than a year before, that in the nuclear

age, adversaries should avoid situations that might put their rivals before a choice between a humiliating retreat or nuclear war. He added that adopting such a policy in the nuclear age, would be only a sign of the bankruptcy of our policy or a collective death wish of the world.

The world – so it seems – is ripe for a new Kennedy.

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